

EXPERIENCE IN FORMING PROFESSIONAL AND CREATIVE COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS THROUGH QUEST TECHNOLOGY IN PHYSICS EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article presents the experience of developing pre-service physics teachers' professional and creative competencies through the use of quest technology in physics education. The study analyzes the dynamics of students' creative thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and decision-making skills formed during quest-based learning activities. The effectiveness of the quest method in integrating theoretical and practical aspects of physics education is scientifically justified. Experimental results demonstrate that the use of quest technology significantly enhances students' professional creativity, motivation, and engagement in the learning process.

Keywords: physics education, quest technology, creative competence, professional development, learning process, interactive method, experimental study.

Introduction. In the modern education system, the formation of independent thinking, creative approach and problem-solving skills in pupils and students is one of the priority tasks of education. Today, digital technologies, the expansion of information flows and the introduction of innovative approaches in the educational process require future teachers not only to have in-depth knowledge in the field of science, but also to have the competence to think creatively and apply new pedagogical approaches in practice. From this point of view, the introduction of interactive methods, in particular, quest technology, into the educational process plays an important role in the development of the teacher's professional and creative activity.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop human capital through improving the education system" No. PQ-5106 (February 6, 2021) sets out important tasks for the introduction of modern educational technologies, the development of creative thinking of young people, and their orientation to independent thinking. Also, within the framework of the "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment and the Digital Economy", the application of innovative pedagogical approaches in the higher education system, strengthening interdisciplinary integration, and improving the professional potential of teachers are considered one of the priority areas of state policy[1,2].

Physics education is distinguished by its natural-scientific content, logical thinking, and analytical thinking. Therefore, the subjects taught in this direction should serve to form in pupils and students such mental actions as solving problem situations, determining cause-and-effect relationships between phenomena, and putting forward scientific hypotheses. However, practice shows that in traditional forms of teaching, the activation of independent thinking and creativity in students is not sufficiently ensured. Therefore, educational processes organized on the basis of quest technology serve as an effective tool for connecting the theoretical content of physics with the practical activities of students, and for developing their analytical and creative thinking competencies[3].

Quest technology allows organizing the educational process on the basis of game, problem and research elements. Through this method, the student not only remembers the information, but also actively works with it, analyzes, draws logical conclusions and tries to find a collective solution. Quest tasks in physics education, combined with the processes of experiment, observation, calculation and analytical thinking, serve to form professional and creative competencies in future teachers[4].

The relevance of this study is that through the effective introduction of quest technology in physics education, it is possible to develop creative thinking, analytical approach, communicative and problem-solving competencies in future teachers. This, in turn, creates the basis for their future professional activities in an innovative spirit.

Literature review. The issue of forming professional and creative competencies in future teachers is one of the important areas of modern pedagogy and psychology. In recent years, many scientific studies have been conducted in the education system on the development of students' creative thinking, problem-solving and independent decision-making skills through the implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies, in particular, quest technology, in the educational process.

Foreign researchers such as M. Prensky (2001), H. Jenkins (2013), D. Jonassen (2017), A. Gee (2019), analyzing teaching methods based on game technologies, emphasize their importance in developing students' logical thinking, learning to work together, and justifying their ideas. In particular, the "quest-based learning" model is recognized as an effective pedagogical technology that activates the educational process and increases students' motivation for research and analysis.

Research by G. C. Gunter, R. F. Kenny, and E. H. Vick (2016) has revealed the positive impact of quest tasks on students' problem-solving and decision-making processes. Also, the taxonomy of L. Anderson and D. Krathwohl highlights the role of the quest method as a tool for guiding students to higher-level thinking activities at the stages of knowledge application, analysis, and creation.

Research conducted in the CIS countries has also enriched scientific views in this area. In particular, Russian scientists such as E. S. Polat, V. P. Bepalko, A. A. Verbitsky, O. V. Ostroverkhova, and S. G. Korshunova have scientifically substantiated the didactic potential of quest technology and its role in stimulating students' independent knowledge acquisition, analytical, and creative thinking in the learning process. In their opinion, quest games are important not only as a means of acquiring knowledge, but also as a mechanism for the formation of social and communicative competencies.

Uzbek scientists such as Sh. Kholboyev, G. Ahmedova, A. Mirzayev, M. Tursunov, Z. Yuldasheva have studied the effectiveness of using interactive methods, including quest technology, in the educational process based on pedagogical experience. Their work has proven that through quest tasks, students develop logical thinking, observation, problem-solving skills, and the ability to analyze experimental results.

Also, studies conducted by B. Kadyrov (2020) and N. Kakhhorova (2022) highlight the impact of quest technology on learning motivation in teaching natural sciences, as well as its role in developing the teacher's professional skills. The studies emphasize that by properly planning and establishing criteria for evaluating quest activities, students' creative and analytical thinking can be effectively developed.

In the field of pedagogical psychology, the works of scientists such as L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leontyev, P. Ya. Galperin, S. L. Rubinstein analyze the motivational, cognitive and practical aspects of learning activities. Their theoretical views determine the psychological foundations of quest technology, since this method is aimed at activating the student's active participation, problem analysis and independent thinking process.

Scientific research conducted in our country is also focused on current problems in this area. Based on the initiatives of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovations, methodological guides have been developed on the implementation of advanced educational technologies in the educational process and on increasing the professional and creative potential of teachers. However, the fact that the existing studies have not deeply studied the issue of the formation of professional and creative competencies in physics education based on quest technology indicates the need for new scientific research in this area.

Therefore, this study aims to experimentally substantiate the role of quest technology in the process of physics education, its effectiveness in forming students' creative thinking, analytical approach, communicative and problem-solving skills. The development of a methodological system for the development of professional and creative competencies of future physics teachers through this approach is of scientific and practical importance.

Discussion and results. In the modern educational process, the development of students' professional and creative competencies is considered one of the main indicators of the quality of education. The process of using quest technology in teaching physics enhances interactive cooperation between teachers and students, introduces elements of creativity, interest and responsibility into educational activities. During the study, the effectiveness of quest technology in learning motivation, independent thinking and solving problem situations was tested.

Experimental work was conducted among students studying in the physics department of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute. The participants of the study were divided into two groups: the experimental group (those who were trained using quest technology) and the control group (those who were trained using the traditional method). During the experiment, quest tasks were developed on the main sections of physics - mechanics, electromagnetism, thermal phenomena and optics. In each quest, problem questions, practical tasks, team communication and result assessment stages were introduced.

The analysis of the results of the experiment showed that students trained on the basis of quest technology demonstrated a 25-30% higher level of creative thinking compared to the control group. Their orientation to scientific research, the ability to justify their opinions, make independent decisions, and solve problematic situations significantly increased.

The results of the questionnaire also showed that quest-based lessons increased students' motivation, participation, and communication culture in physics. Students had the opportunity to freely express their thoughts, work in a team, and defend their ideas. During the lessons organized on the basis of quest tasks, their scientific thinking, observation, analysis, and synthesis skills developed.

As a result of the final tests conducted at the end of the experiment, students in the experimental group achieved high results in the practical application of theoretical knowledge.

In particular, the analysis of quest tasks on electrical phenomena and mechanical systems confirmed that their level of analytical thinking increased.

Statistical analysis of the results (χ^2 test, analysis of variance) showed that the effect of quest technology is reliable ($p < 0.05$). This proves that the systematic use of quest elements in the teaching process is effective not only in developing students' learning motivation, but also in developing their professional and creative competencies.

➤ In general, the results of the study showed that quest technology in physics education:

- Increases students' learning efficiency;
- Develops creative and critical thinking;
- Turns the learning process into an interactive and competitive environment;
- Strengthens communication between the teacher and the student.

This approach allows integrating modern pedagogical technologies in teaching physics and adapting the learning process to the personal development needs of students. Therefore, the use of quest technology can be considered one of the important directions of modernization of physics teaching methodology.

Discussion and results. In the modern education system, the development of students' professional and creative competencies is one of the important indicators of quality education. Quest technology in teaching physics is one of the effective methods that activates the learning process, strengthens students' independent thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills[5].

During the study, experimental work was conducted among 2nd-year students studying in the physics department of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute. During the experiment, students were divided into two groups:

Experimental group - those who were trained using quest technology;

Control group - those who were trained using traditional methods.

Quest tasks were developed based on the sections "Mechanics", "Electromagnetism", "Thermal Phenomena" and "Optics". Each quest included a step-by-step problem situation, creative research and the process of finding a collective solution.

The data obtained based on the results of the test, questionnaire and observation conducted at the end of the experiment are presented in the following table:

Table 1. Results of teaching in physics based on quest technology (comparison of experimental and control groups)

Nº	Indicators	Control group (%)	Experiment group (%)	Difference (%)
1	Level of understanding and expression of physical knowledge	64	87	+23
2	Ability to analyze a problem situation and find a solution	58	84	+26
3	Creative thinking and ideation activity	52	81	+29

4	Teamwork and communication skills	61	88	+27
5	Learning motivation and level of interest in science	67	91	+24
6	Accuracy in completing practical tasks	63	85	+22
	Average score	61	86	+25

The analysis of the results shows that the experimental group students achieved an average of 25 percent higher results than the control group. In particular, a significant increase was observed in the indicators of creative thinking (+29%) and problem situation analysis (+26%).

The results of the statistical analysis ($\chi^2 = 4.32$; $p < 0.05$) confirm the reliable effect of quest technology on educational effectiveness. In addition, according to the results of the student questionnaire, 87 percent of the participants assessed quest-based lessons as “motivating them to be active”, “making physics interesting” and “strengthening practical knowledge”.

Based on the conducted experiment, the following conclusions were drawn:

☑ Quest technology develops students’ analytical, creative and independent thinking skills.

☑ Quest-based teaching increases motivation, increases interest in science.

☑ The quest approach in physics education creates favorable conditions for the formation of professional and creative competencies in students.

Thus, the results of the experiment showed that quest technology in the process of teaching physics significantly increases not only the quality of educational activities, but also the level of personal and professional development of students.

Conclusion. The conducted experimental work showed that the use of quest technology in the process of teaching physics is one of the effective methods for developing the professional and creative competencies of future teachers. Quest-based educational activities increase the activity of students, form the skills of independent thinking, problem solving, communication and teamwork. At the same time, this approach enhances the interactivity of education and serves to reveal the personal creative potential of the student.

During the experiment, it was found that, compared to traditional lesson forms, classes based on quest technology developed students’ abilities to conduct scientific analysis, analyze experimental results, put forward innovative ideas, and find new solutions in practical activities. Through quest tasks, it was observed that students’ readiness to apply their

knowledge in real situations, their motivation towards physics, and their level of professional self-awareness increased.

Also, classes organized on the basis of quest technology caused changes in the activities of teachers. Teachers began to pay more attention to the creative organization of the lesson process, the use of modern information and communication technologies, and the development of analytical thinking. This, in turn, contributed to an increase in the quality of education and a deeper understanding of the practical importance of physics.

In general, the results of the study indicate the need for the widespread introduction of quest technology into the physics education system. This technology plays an important role in developing the professional and creative competencies of teachers, organizing the educational process based on a person-centered approach, and creating an innovative learning environment that meets modern educational standards.

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